

STATUS AND OPPORTUNITIES OF TEAK (*Tectona grandis* Linn. f) CULTIVATION IN NORTHEAST INDIAAbishek Nongtri¹, Emacaree S Nongtri¹, Baby Lalremruati² and Lyngdoh N^{1*}¹Biodiversity Research Centre, Environmental Science Department, Mizoram University, Tanhril, Aizawl- 796004²Environmental Science Department, Mizoram University, Tanhril, Aizawl- 796004Corresponding Author: lyngdoh@gmail.com

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Abstract

Teak (Tectona grandis L.f.) is one of the world's most valuable tropical hardwood species due to its superior timber quality, natural durability, and high economic returns. Although naturally distributed in peninsular India and Southeast Asia, teak has been extensively introduced into Northeast (NE) India, where it has emerged as a promising plantation species. This review synthesises the current status, ecological suitability, economic prospects, and challenges associated with teak cultivation in the region. Teak plantations are widely distributed across Assam, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Manipur, Nagaland, and Tripura, predominantly within tropical moist deciduous forest zones. The humid monsoonal climate, characterized by annual rainfall of 1,750–2,500 mm and temperatures ranging from 18–40 °C, closely matches the species' ecological requirements. Strengthening research on genetic improvement, site-specific management practices, and wood characterization, coupled with effective collaboration between research institutions and state agencies, will be essential for developing NE India as a major teak-producing region and reducing India's dependence on imported teak timber.

Keywords: agroforestry, timber production, cultivation, plantation forestry, challenges

Introduction

Teak (*Tectona grandis* L. f., family Lamiaceae), (Wagstaff and Olmstead 1997) is a diploid ($2n = 36$), insect-pollinated tree native to South East Asia. Its natural range may be divided into three disjunct regions (Hedegart 1976): (1) Central and South India, (2) Myanmar, Laos, and North West Thailand, and (3) Indonesia (especially Central and East Java, and some geographically close islands such as Muna and Betung). The centre of origin of this species is presumed to be in Myanmar (Meniaud 1930). In India, teak is naturally confined to the Indian peninsular region south of 24 ° north latitude. The northern limit of its distribution is in the western Aravallis in Rajputana at 24 ° north latitude, and southwards it extends up to Travancore. However, the distribution is discontinuous, where large chunks of the forest are found in the states of Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Tamil Nadu, Karnataka and Kerala. Large-scale extraction of teak was initially started during the early 19th century, and by the turn of the century much of the natural resources were depleted. In order to replenish the stock, efforts were initiated to raise plantations of teak in suitable areas, and in India, this was started during the year 1846 at Nilambur, Kerala. Currently, it is one of the most planted species in the country and now accounts for 44 percent of the world's teak plantations, covering an area of 4.35 million hectares (Masilamani et al. 2021). States of Andhra Pradesh (along with present Telangana), Chhattisgarh, Gujarat, Karnataka, Madhya Pradesh, Maharashtra, Mizoram, Tripura and Uttar Pradesh have teak plantation areas of more than 100,000 ha.

Commercial and Ecological Importance

Teak is a valuable tropical hardwood known for its superior quality, durability, stability, and appearance (Palanisamy et al., 2009). Its natural resistance to decay, fungi, termites, and weather makes it ideal for shipbuilding, furniture, outdoor equipment, joinery, carpentry, and high-quality sawn timber (Miranda et al., 2011; Palanisamy et al., 2009). The attractive grain and color enhance its use in decorative products and handicrafts (Lukmandaru et al., 2016). Plantation-grown teak harvested young also has acceptable properties for indoor and outdoor uses (Wanneng et al., 2014). Residues from processing can be used for renewable energy, as lignin in teak residues has high calorific value and energy potential (Oluwadare et al., 2016).

Teak provides substantial ecological and environmental benefits. Teak plantations function as important carbon sinks by sequestering atmospheric carbon dioxide and storing carbon in woody biomass, thereby contributing to climate change mitigation and ecosystem sustainability (Upadhyay et al., 2021). The species is extensively utilized

in afforestation, reforestation, and forest restoration programmes due to its adaptability to a wide range of tropical environments (Palanisamy et al., 2009). Furthermore, it contributes to soil stabilization and erosion control through its extensive root systems and can assist in the rehabilitation of degraded lands (Watanabe et al., 2010). The maintenance of forest cover through teak plantations also supports biodiversity conservation and reduces harvesting pressure on natural forests, thereby promoting sustainable forest management (Upadhyay et al., 2021).

Trade and Market

The economic importance of teak is reflected in global trade statistics. Although teak represents only a minor portion of global tropical timber production, it significantly impacts the international timber trade value due to its premium market position. Recent global assessments indicate that teak resources are now distributed across more than 80 tropical countries, reflecting the rapid expansion of plantation forestry beyond its natural range (Kollert et al., 2024). International teak trade is largely driven by Asian markets, particularly India, which accounts for approximately 97% of global teak roundwood imports sourced from more than 40 exporting countries. Between 2009 and 2019, about 10 million m³ of teak wood in the rough (Fig 1) has been imported. India's dominant role has sustained demand for plantation-grown teak and encouraged plantation expansion worldwide (Kollert et al., 2024). The market value of teak varies substantially according to origin, age, diameter, and wood quality. Premium mature teak logs from Myanmar have historically commanded import prices ranging from USD 800–1,050 m⁻³ (approximately ₹66,000–87,000 m⁻³), whereas plantation-grown teak from Africa and Latin America generally trades between USD 300–440 m⁻³ (approximately ₹25,000–37,000 m⁻³). In Southeast Asia, Grade-A plantation teak logs have been reported to sell at USD 250–321 m⁻³ (approximately ₹21,000–27,000 m⁻³), illustrating the significant influence of grading and timber quality on commercial value. These price differences demonstrate why teak plantations are increasingly viewed as valuable long-term forestry investments.

Teak in North East

The North East (NE) India is located between two patches of natural teak-growing areas of the world, Central India and Myanmar. However, the region now has a sizable portion of its forest cover under teak plantation, especially in the states of Assam, Meghalaya, Mizoram, Manipur, and Tripura. Teak plantation in the northeast is believed to have gained momentum during the last quarter of the 20th century. Presently, it is seen as one of the promising plantation species. Many state governments and

corporate agencies are promoting teak as a plantation species in barren places, private lands, and farmers' fields. Recently, on 3rd June 2026, the government of Tripura has rolled out a large-scale scientific teak

plantation programme across the state with estimated earnings of up to Rs. 2.5 crores over a 20–25-year cycle from 1-2ha of land.

Fig 1: Teak round wood imports trend from 2009 to 2019 (Source: Kant and Nautiyal, 2021)

Teak growing areas in the north-east

North-east India accounts for 23.61% of the total forest cover of the country (FSI 2023), covering an area of approximately 168,903 km². The region is home to all six major forest types and thirteen of the sixteen groupings. In the north-east, teak is generally planted in the Tropical moist deciduous forests, a forest type found in all states of the region, except Arunachal Pradesh (Table 1). It can be seen that moist deciduous forests form a large part of the states of Meghalaya, Mizoram, Nagaland, and Tripura. These forests are generally distributed along the foothills and valley regions. In Meghalaya, teak plantations can be found on the northern slope of the Shillong plateau and a major part of the East and West Garo hills of Meghalaya. Teak plantations are also maintained by the district autonomous council of the state (Plate No 1). In Manipur, teak occurs in close association with *Dipterocarpus tuberculatus* along the Myanmar border. Across the state, it is extensively planted along road sides and surrounding ponds (Plates No. 2 & 3). Teak has been extensively planted across the state of Tripura under the National Afforestation Programme (Chakraborty 1985; Anonymous 2000) for the

quick restoration of degraded forests. These plantations are scattered in all districts of the state. As per available records, among the northeastern states, teak was first planted at Makum, Assam, at the end of the 18th century (Plate 4). Presently, teak plantations dominate areas under Kamrup, Nagaon, Hailakandi, Bongaigaon, and Karbi Anglong. In Mizoram, teak is generally found in the western and central parts of the state, mostly near rivers. Some of the districts where teak plantations are commonly sighted are Mamit, Kolasib, Aizawl, and Lunglei. Teak has become one of the main tree species of Nagaland. Its plantations spread in areas of Dimapur, Chumoukedima (Plate 5), Niuland, and along the Assam border in the districts of Wokha, Mokokchung, Longleng, Mon, and Peren. A recent record of the area under teak cultivation is not available. However, based on the Forest Sector Report India 2010, published by the Indian Council of Forestry Research and Education, the total area under teak plantation in India is reported to be 42,06,201 acres. The details of the area under teak plantation in the 5 north eastern states where it is planted are given in Table 1.

Table 1: State-wise area under Tropical moist deciduous forests and area under teak plantation (ha) in different North East states

Sl. No.	Sites	Area (m ²)	Percentage of Land (%)	Area (ha)
1.	Assam	5106.98	17.80	29,872
2.	Manipur	4451.11	25.08	150
3.	Meghalaya	8709	47.56	Not available
4.	Mizoram	5897.13	32.21	129,000
5.	Nagaland	2899.32	37.95	6,500
6.	Sikkim	190.98	5.03	Not available
7.	Tripura	3026.86	38.94	156,850

Source: Forest Sector Report India-2010

Climatic and edaphic suitability of the region

Teak is naturally adapted to warm and humid environments characterized by seasonal rainfall patterns and distinct wet and dry. The climatic conditions prevailing in North East India closely correspond to the environmental requirements considered optimal for teak (*Tectona grandis*) growth in other parts of India. Teak is generally reported to perform best in regions receiving 1,200–2,500 mm of annual rainfall, warm temperatures, and a distinct dry season that promotes wood formation and seasonal growth (Palanisamy et al., 2009; Neetha et al., 2017). Similarly, tropical moist deciduous forests of North East India experience a humid monsoonal climate characterized by annual rainfall ranging from approximately 1,750 to 2,500 mm, high relative humidity, and temperatures varying between 18 and 40 °C (Wapongnungsang et al., 2021; Kalita&Yumnam, 2025).

Compared with several teak-growing regions of India that receive lower annual rainfall and experience more pronounced dry conditions, the climatic regime of North East India provides a consistently moist and thermally favourable environment that supports the successful establishment, persistence, and productivity of teak plantations. The widespread occurrence of teak within tropical moist deciduous forests across the region further indicates that the warm temperatures, abundant rainfall, and seasonal moisture fluctuations characteristic of North East India are highly conducive to teak growth and development.

Teak can grow under a wide range of edaphic conditions. However, it generally prefers deep, well-drained soils rich in essential nutrients, slightly acid to alkali and high base content, especially calcium. Plantations established on soils with higher exchangeable calcium and nutrient availability generally exhibit superior growth and timber productivity (Noda et al., 2021; Ashick Rajah et al., 2025). The northeast

soil is characterized by a range of textural types: silty clay, silty loam, loamy clay, and loamy sand. The soil in the region is high in organic matter, which can play a crucial role in teak productivity by improving soil structure, enhancing water-holding capacity, and promoting nutrient cycling. Across north-eastern India, teak plantation soils have been reported to contain surface soil organic carbon contents ranging from approximately 2.1% to 2.7%, with total soil organic carbon stocks reaching 44.66 Mg C ha⁻¹ within the upper 45 cm soil profile (Kenye et al., 2019). Wehr et al. (2017) identified soil organic carbon contents of 1–6% as important determinants of teak establishment and early growth. A growth-limiting factor in the soil of the north-east is the acidity. Nearly 65% of soils are suffering from strong acidity (pH < 5.5; Sharma et al., 2006). However, this can be controlled by soil amendment practices, such as liming, to provide better growing conditions and avoid aluminum toxicity.

Opportunities

Teakwood for the local market

Among wood sources, teak is a timber species with high use value for furniture making. It is reportedly the most commonly used species in wooden furniture production in India. Teak accounts for almost 50% of the total wooden furniture produced; sal and deodar account for about 20%, and the balance includes mahogany, cedar, and other tree types (ITTO). Teak furniture products are highly valued and afforded only by rich families. The richest 20% of the Indian population consumes 47% of the total teak fabricated round blocks. Teak wood has immense potential to boost the furniture sector of the region. The high demand for the wood and its products, both locally and nationally, can upscale plantation levels, create markets, and encourage small and medium industries. The current market price of teak in Aizawl city ranges between ₹1,500 and ₹1,700 per cubic foot (cft), much higher than pine, which is ₹ 550/cft and other softwood species (₹ 550- 800/cft). In Assam, the cost ranges between ₹2500-3000/ cft, in Nagaland between ₹1000-1500/cft, in Tripura between ₹1000-1500/cft, and between ₹1200-1500/cft in Meghalaya. In many of the northeastern states, the wood furniture business is a significant livelihood activity. In the state of Manipur, as many as 191 wood-based furniture industries consume 12441.24m³ of timber annually. In Mizoram, teak wood furniture is the most expensive. Prices for a single door can range from ₹15,000 to 20000, while a sofa set can reach ₹75000, and a simple TV stand can fetch between ₹20000 and 25000/- (Plate No.10 to 13). However, the supply of teak wood to the market is in decline, and teak wood furniture is afforded only by well-off-families. Therefore, there is large opportunity for private and public teak cultivation to bridge the supply gap, making it more affordable.

Integration into farming systems

Teak for small farmers

In India, Agroforestry is the name for land-use systems and practices in which woody perennials are deliberately integrated with crops and/or animals on the same land-management unit. In north-east India, besides the traditional forms of agroforestry, such as shifting cultivation and home gardens, that are practiced across the region, specific local practices and modern AGF models are also encountered. In many of the reports, teak is considered one of the priority perennial components of an AGF system. For instance, in the states of Manipur and Meghalaya, it is grown in blocks and on farm boundaries along with agricultural and horticultural crops (Plates 6 to 8), and is a dominant species in homegardens (Ulman et al 2022). In Tripura, teak is grown in jhum lands (Plate no. 9) and integrated in some of the modern two and three-tier AGF models. In the two-tier model, it is grown solely with ginger or black pepper, while in a more complex model, banana is integrated as well (Sarkar et al 2022). In Nagaland teak is planted by farmers as part of an assisted regeneration project for fallow lands (Faminow et al 2000).

Global evidence suggests that teak-based AGF systems enable farmers to diversify farm production, reduce risk, support food security, and generate income, which can have wide potential in the region. However, teak should not be seen as a crop that can bring quick returns because a minimum of 15-16 years is required to obtain a final yield with sufficient wood of acceptable quality to cope with preferred international market standards. Farmers are to cultivate teak as living saving accounts where teak is harvested to finance significant cash needs such as weddings, school fees, large medical expenses, social commitments, or emergencies (Perdana et al., 2012)

Short rotation teak

Short rotation forestry is cultivating fast-growing tree species for the production of woody biomass as a renewable resource. Trees are usually felled when they are 10–20 cm wide at breast height, which takes between 5 and 25 years depending on the tree species. Teak is traditionally harvested at ages between 40 and 60 years old for higher returns. However, with proper management and more intensive inputs, rotation ages can be reduced to 20 to 25 years. Some of the features that favor teak are the space made available for intercropping during initial years before canopy closure, retention of superior wood properties, and efficient coppicing ability of teak. However, the venture is more applicable to farmers with larger land holdings who can afford more intensive inputs such as tissue-cultured clones, fertigation, and high-density planting. The harvested materials have applications as small-diameter commercial timber, veneer, and poles, which can be used locally.

Teak for land reclamation

According to the National Remote Sensing Centre (2019), 4.60 m ha, or 18.2% of the total ground area in the northeast region, is reported to be degraded. About 30% (1.42 m ha) of this is due to water erosion, and the remaining 70% (3.35 m ha) is due to various other forms of deterioration, including acidity of the soil, waterlogging, barren rocks, mining, quarrying, riverine sands, and industrial effluents. Some of the prominent causes are shifting cultivation, mining, and the oil industries. Some of the states with a high percentage of land degradation are Nagaland (47.1%), Mizoram (34.92%), Manipur (33.21%), and Meghalaya (28.38%). One of the recommended strategies of land reclamation, besides soil working and nutrient management, is combining seasonal crops and multipurpose trees such as teak. Teak-based intercropping was reported to have a significant build-up of SOC stock compared to under-cultivated land in abandoned *jhum* land sites of Tripura (Yadav et al. 2021). Teak plantations are a potential option for improving ecosystem carbon storage in degraded soils of hill ecosystems in Mizoram (Lungmuana et al 2025). Teak was one of the plantation species that performed well in the rehabilitation of mine overburden by the South Eastern Coalfield Ltd. (SECL) in Madhya Pradesh and Chhattisgarh (Thakur et al. 2022). Another potential use of teak is phytoremediation of oil-contaminated habitats, especially in the oil-producing areas of Assam. Observations on 3-month-old teak seedlings grown in crude oil-contaminated media showed no drastic reduction in growth, displaying its phytoremediation potential (Agbogidi et al., 2007). Among the tree species *T. grandis*, *G. arborea*, *A. indica*, and *M. champaca* grown in crude oil-contaminated drill sites in Assam, teak showed the highest survival rate and height growth after 24 months (Yenn et al 2014).

Challenges

There is immense scope for teak cultivation in the northeast to augment local timber supply, increase farm income, promote small and medium-scale industries, and enhance ecological services. However, teak cultivation among farmers is a recent activity, and therefore, certain challenges and issues are highlighted below;

Although many plantations have reached the rotation age, there are many scientific aspects that have been ignored during the planting process

In almost all plantations, there is no exact record of the age and the source of planting material. Using unimproved and unidentified planting material, especially in many of the government plantations, is bound to compromise the growth and timber quality of trees.

Farmers lack knowledge of the standard package and practices for teak, which, like any other commercial tree crop, requires care, tending, pruning, and thinning, for higher productivity. Consequently, teak growers in the region will not receive the expected monetary benefits.

Low pH of soil across the region can have a significant effect on wood properties, and therefore, proper soil testing and recommended soil amendment practices should be adopted

The economic and ecological feasibility of teak-based agro-forestry models in the region needs to be scientifically evaluated before recommending to farmers

Characterizing general wood features and testing the physical, mechanical, and chemical properties of teak wood from the region is essential for assigning any market value.

Legal formalities to be followed for the cultivation and harvesting of teak

Therefore, strengthening scientific research on teak in the region is essential. Priority areas include proper site selection, identification of superior seed sources, genetic improvement, and the development of standardized cultivation packages and management practices. At this early stage, close collaboration between research organizations and state forest departments is critical to generate reliable knowledge, support successful plantation establishment, and build farmers' confidence in teak cultivation. Teak has been successfully introduced in more than 80 countries worldwide, demonstrating remarkable adaptability and substantial economic value. India currently imports significant quantities of teak timber from several teak-growing countries, particularly Ecuador, Ghana, Costa Rica, Panama, Brazil, Côte d'Ivoire, and Benin. In this context, Northeast India possesses considerable potential to emerge as a major teak-producing region within the country. With suitable climatic conditions and increasing interest in cultivation forestry, the region could not only meet local timber requirements but also contribute significantly to reducing India's dependence on imported teak and augment the national supply of high-quality teak wood.

Photo Plates

1. Teak Plantation inside Khasi Hills Autonomous District Council forest, Nongpoh, Meghalaya

2. Roadside plantation of Teak inside Manipur University Campus, Imphal, Manipur (Courtesy: Dr. Loushambam Romechand Singh)

3. Teak surrounding a pond in Thoubal, Manipur (Courtesy: Dr. Loushambam Romechand Singh)

4. Forest Department Teak plantations in Makum, Assam

5. Forest Department Plantation at Molvum, Chumoukedima, Nagaland (Courtesy: Mr. Imkongsunep Longchar)

6. Block plantation of Teak in Garo Hills, Meghalaya (Courtesy: Dr. Kalkame Ch Momin)

7. Boundary Plantation of Teak surrounding paddy field in Thoubal, Manipur (Courtesy: Dr. Loushambam Romeechand Singh)

8. Teak surrounding sesame field in Mendipathar, Meghalaya (Courtesy: Mr. Archan Rabha)

9. Teak trees in Jhum Field, Sonaimuri, Tripura (Courtesy: Dr. Subrata Das)

10. Teak Wood sofa sets in Aizawl, Mizoram

11. Teak Wood Bed in Aizawl, Mizoram

12. Teak Wood doors in Aizawl, Mizoram

13. Teak Wood TV stand in Aizawl, Mizoram

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